

RESEARCH ON COMBUSTION BEHAVIOR OF HYBRID COMPOSITE BY FIRE DYNAMICS SIMULATOR

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Introduction

Necessity

- Recently, composite materials have been used in various fields such as construction and aviation, **which require improved flame retardancy**.
- However, it is disadvantageous that large structures are costly and time consuming to perform these experiments.

Objective

- In this study, fire model of **Carbon/Epoxy composites** and **Carbon/Jute/Epoxy Composites** is investigated by analyzing the behavior of heat release rate generated in the event of fire using the Fire Dynamics Simulator (FDS) based on CFD.

Methodology

FDS modeling

- Combustion model was developed for obtaining the combustion behavior of 100 X 100 square specimen. The overall grid size, ie mesh arrangement, was determined using a **grid selection method**.
- In the case of completely enclosed space, the oxygen is not supplied, the fire is suppressed, So the space is set as a partially **open space**.
- Basic properties of carbon fiber, jute fiber and epoxy are measured by **TGA and DSC equipment**.

Fig. 2 Composite Model

Combustion test

- Heat Release Rate measurement
- Using **Cone Calorimeter (FFT, England)**
- 100(mm)x100(mm) maximum thickness of 50(mm)
- Conduct a cone calorimeter test at least twice
- Test carried out in accordance with ISO5660-1
- Test Environment: 25.0°C, 99.6 kPa

Results

Compare results

Fig. 4 Comparison of HRR data

- For FDS analysis, it represents a **steeper slope** than the actual experiment because it is calculated using the theoretical equation
- Since the **theoretical equation** is used, it is impossible to apply changes in the actual environment and chemical composition
- Combustion behavior is similar but error occurs because it is applied under the premise that **the material's properties don't change**
- **Correct environment and material's properties** are needed to reduce these errors

Conclusion

Fig. 6 Preparation of hybrid composite

Fig. 7 composite's HRR

- **In this study**, we compared the burning behavior of the composite materials of FDS. As a result, some errors are generated, but the combustion behavior is similar.
- Research is needed to accurately **implement factors and surroundings** that affect ignition time and behavior in order to reduce errors